

BASIC ENGLISH TEACHING SKILLS AND STUDENTS' INTEREST IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: *This article describes the study/teaching of English in the elementary grades of secondary general education, which requires the use of special teaching methods. teaching methodology is a holistic system, consisting of such components as educational conditions, purpose, content, method and means.*

Keywords: *Speech skills, analysis, definition, assistance, goals and tasks.*

Introduction: This is a discussion of issues related to the process of teaching English oral speech to primary school students, and its subject is "oral speech skills". classes form the methodological basis of the formation system in English language education.especially starting from elementary school, to increase students' interest in learning English, one of the most important elements in learning a foreign language is to build vocabulary and learn by combining learned words and making simple sentences to strengthen the words rgangan,using visual aids, memorizing words belonging to the same group, colors, days of the week, months, seasons and similar words in the form of poetry leaves a deep impression on the child's mind.

Main part: The goals and objectives of the research. The main goal of the research is to analyze and study the methodological features of the formation of "speaking and listening comprehension skills", which are a component of the

activity of oral communication in a foreign language. the realization of this goal, in turn, requires the following tasks:- to determine the place and essence of oral speech in teaching foreign languages and to achieve this goal by studying linguistic, pedagogical, methodical literature on the subject and using them critically;

-distinguish between speaking and listening comprehension, which are types of oral speech, and comparative study and analysis of their place in language education;

- to study the role of knowledge about the phonetic system of the native language and the possibilities of relying on it in the formation of oral speech skills;

- analysis of the coverage of oral speech material in English language textbooks and training manuals intended for elementary grades;

- to analyze the system of exercises aimed at the formation of oral speech skills in elementary school textbooks and to summarize the instructions on the use of their effective types;

- to define the principles of implementation of given methodical instructions and to show methodical ways, etc. k. z.

The scientific hypothesis of the research is as follows: in order to help the primary school students to acquire the skills of English speaking and its use in speech communication, the main factor of quick and easy achievement is the purpose of foreign language education it is related to the organization of the study in the direction. the use of linguistic features of the selected language material, interlinguistic typology indicators and the use of exercises based on the consideration of language-related speech situations shows a positive effect on the formation of students' speaking skills.

conclusion: As a result of such a situation, the demand for new foreign language curricula, textbooks, study guides, scientific works, and highly qualified

foreign language teachers is increasing day by day. So let's never get tired of learning. Any person who makes an effort, no matter what field he is in, will definitely achieve his goal.

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